

ISic3516

I.Sicily inscription 3516

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido, sep.87

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3566

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [D(is)·M(anibus)·]
2. Ofiliae · [M(arci)·f(iliae)]
3. Sabinae · M(arcus) · Sau
4. feius · Sabinus · p(osuit)
5. fil(iae)· piissimae · et
6. Ofiliae · Ursae ·
7. coniugi · et · sibi
8. libert(is) · libertab(usque)
9. post(erisque) · eorumomn(ium)

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 and photograph

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld, for Ofilia Sabina, daughter of Marcus, Marcus Saufeius Sabinus set this up for his most pious daughter and for his wife, Ofilia

Ursa and for himself and their freedmen, freedwomen and all their descendants

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284773

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EDCS 14805795

PHI 313632

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 7

Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 143 fig.16

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